

THE CONDENSATION OF α -SUBSTITUTED ACETOACETATES WITH PHENOLS. PART IV. THE CONDENSATION OF CRESOLS AND OTHER LESS REACTIVE PHENOLS WITH ETHYL α -(α -HYDROXY- $\beta\beta\beta$ -TRICHLORO-ETHYL)-ACETOACETATE.

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In continuation of Part III, ethyl α -(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-acetoacetate has been condensed with less reactive phenols. The effect of CH (OH) CCl₃ as α -substituent in acetoacetic ester on the course of the reaction has been discussed.

In Part III of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 113) the authors showed that ethyl α -(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-acetoacetate condensed with different phenols, forming 3-(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-4-methylcoumarin derivatives. The above condensation with less reactive phenols like phenol, cresols, β -naphthol, hydroquinone and resacetophenone is described in this part.

Phenol does not give any solid product. Cresols give interesting results. Preliminary experiments indicate that cresols do not undergo the condensation with ethyl α -(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-acetoacetate in presence of sulphuric acid at ordinary temperature. It is, however, observed that *p*-cresol condenses with sulphuric acid as condensing agent at lower temperatures and a satisfactory yield of 4:6-dimethyl-3-(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-coumarin is obtained by allowing the reaction mixture to remain in a refrigerator for nearly 30 hours. This reaction has also been tried in presence of phosphorus pentoxide to get a chromone, but it does not succeed. Phosphorus oxychloride also proves unsuccessful.

Ortho- and *meta*-cresols, in presence of sulphuric acid alone, give no definite condensation product. The use of alcohol as a solvent facilitates the condensation and a crystalline product could be obtained. An important observation has been made that carbon dioxide is being evolved during the course of the reaction. The purified condensation product from *o*-cresol melts sharply at 186-87°, and the analytical results agree with the formula C₁₂H₁₀O₂Cl₃. It dissolves in alkali and in concentrated sulphuric acid with a yellow colour. Evidently, the pyrone ring is not formed, *i.e.* the condensation has not taken place in *ortho* position to OH. Assuming that the

reaction takes place in *para* position to OH, as it is more probable, the following scheme represents the course of the reaction :

Of the two alternative structures for the condensation product, the structure (B) is preferred as the product gives (a) a mono-acetyl derivative, and (b) it also gives derivatives characteristic of CO group, *e.g.* semicarbazone.

To get a pyrone derivative, the condensation has been tried under various conditions with phosphorus pentoxide as well as oxychloride, but the reaction does not succeed.

The behaviour of *m*-cresol is exactly similar to that of *o*-cresol described above. This behaviour of *m*-cresol is noteworthy as the *meta*-substituted phenols are generally reactive and give easily coumarins. *m*-Cresol condenses smoothly with ethyl α -acetoglutarate (Shah and Shah, *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 2075) and acetosuccinate (unpublished) giving the corresponding coumarin-3- acids. Further work on this reaction is being carried out.

The condensation of β -naphthol, quinol and resacetophenone has been tried in presence of sulphuric acid and other condensing agents. No condensation could be effected, either the original phenol being recovered or tarry materials being obtained.

From the results described here and in the previous part, it is clear that the classification of phenols with regard to their reactivity with β -ketonic esters in the Pechmann reaction holds good in case of ethyl α -(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-acetoacetate. Reactive phenols like resorcinol, pyrogallol (*vide* Part III) easily undergo the condensation either in presence of sulphuric acid or phosphorus oxychloride. Phosphorus pentoxide (Simonis' reaction) also gives coumarins though in less yield, whenever the reaction takes place. Less reactive phenols like phenol, β -naphthol etc. do not condense.

The substituent $\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{CCl}_3$, considered in relation to α -ethyl in ethyl α -ethylacetoacetate, appears to be more reactive judging from the experimental results. The reaction in case of resorcinol and other reactive phenols is completed within a shorter period. *p*-Cresol gives the coumarin only at lower temperature, *o*- and *m*-cresols condense in presence of sulphuric acid, though the reaction takes a different course. No chromone derivative has been obtained in any case with phosphorus pentoxide (*cf.* Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 25). These observations are interesting because the group $\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{CCl}_3$ is a very heavy substituent compared to ethyl. The increased reactivity of ethyl α -(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-acetoacetate may be attributed to the presence of OH and CCl_3 groups in the alkyl chain.

EXPERIMENTAL.

4 : 6-Dimethyl-3-(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-coumarin.—Cold concentrated sulphuric acid (15 c. c.) was slowly added to the mixture of *p*-cresol (3 g.) and ethyl α -(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-acetoacetate (7.7 g.) cooled by ice. The mixture was then left in the refrigerator for 30 hours. It was then poured into ice and the substance obtained well washed with water. It was digested with acetone and filtered from the tarry matter. On evaporating the solvent, the greenish crystals obtained were recrystallised from toluene as needles, m. p. 202-3°, yield 1.5 g. (Found : Cl, 33.34. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_3$ requires Cl, 33.11 per cent).

The methyl ether, prepared as usual, crystallised from dilute alcohol, m. p. 207°. (Found : Cl, 30.33, 30.0. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_3\text{Cl}_3, \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cl, 30.10 per cent).

γ -Trichloromethyl- β -(3-methyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)-propylmethyl ketone.—Cold sulphuric acid (78% ; 15 c. c.) was gradually added to the mixture of *o*-cresol (2 g.) and ethyl α -(α -hydroxy- $\beta\beta\beta$ -trichloroethyl)-acetoacetate (5 g.), dissolved in absolute alcohol (12 c. c.) with shaking and cooling. The colour of the solution slowly changed to deep brown on keeping and

carbon dioxide was evolved during the course of the reaction. On the fourth day, the crystals that had separated were collected. The filtrate on further keeping for about 7 days gave a further yield. The product was crystallised from alcohol as feathery crystals, m. p. 186-87°, yield 1 g. (Found : Cl, 36.1. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 36.0 per cent). Glacial acetic acid can be used in place of alcohol, but the yield is less in that case.

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared by acetic anhydride and pyridine, crystallised from dilute alcohol in diamond-shaped crystals, m. p. 75°. (Found : Cl, 31.39. $C_{14}H_{12}O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 31.52 per cent). The *semicarbazone* crystallised from water as rhombic crystals, m. p. 256-57°. (Found : Cl, 29.95. $C_{13}H_{10}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 30.21 per cent).

γ -Trichloromethyl- β -(2-methyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)-propylmethyl ketone. —*m*-Cresol was condensed exactly in the same manner as *o*-cresol. The product was isolated similarly. Carbon dioxide was evolved. The product on crystallisation from acetic acid and then from methyl alcohol gave rectangular plates, m. p. 208-9° (decomp.), yield 0.7 g. (Found : Cl, 35.87. $C_{12}H_{12}O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 36.0 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared as before, crystallised from alcohol in tiny crystals, m. p. 104-5°. (Found : Cl, 31.07. $C_{14}H_{12}O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 31.52 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m. p. 214°. (Found : Cl, 30.04. $C_{13}H_{10}O_2N_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 30.21 per cent).

Phenol, β -naphthol, quinol and resacetophenone could not be condensed even with different condensing agents.

Further work is being continued.

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